

A TRIBUTE to JOHN CAGE CA12G92E2

Fotografie di scena e documentazione della performance presentata
alla XV Florence Biennale, Firenze, 22 ottobre 2025.

*Stage photographs and documentation from the performance
presented at the XV Florence Biennale, Florence, October 22, 2025.*

**FLORENCE[®]
BIENNALE**

**ART+
DESIGN**

5 pm- 6 pm

**Wednesday
22/10**

SERGIO MALTAGLIATI—TRIBUTE TO JOHN CAGE

Presentation

Theatre Area – Spadolini Pavilion

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